

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D7.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation - update M35

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Executive Summary

The empirical research conducted in the COVINFORM project is centred around assessing COVID-19 impact, response, and lessons learnt across diverse local contexts. The empirical research conducted in the context of WP7 specifically aims to explore COVID-19 impact, response and lessons learnt from the perspective of information communication. The current deliverable (D7.8) focuses on synthesizing data that is drawn from WP7 desk research of secondary source and original empirical research. The current deliverable is a synthesis of the analysis conducted in D7.7 (Analysis: Communication and information - update M34), which further drew upon previous deliverables and expert interviews.

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1 Introduction

The COVINFORM project examines the COVID-19 responses at government, public health, community, and information and communication levels. It analyses the impact of the pandemic with a special focus on how vulnerability was acknowledged and addressed by different stakeholders. It draws upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses, as well as residents' perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation.

The project addresses the following top-level research questions, within the target countries and municipalities, across several work packages:

- **RQ1:** How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- **RQ2:** How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- **RQ3:** What were the lived experiences of the pandemic/crisis management within certain vulnerable groups across diverse local contexts?
- **RQ4:** Which barriers, unintended consequences, trade-offs, lessons learnt and promising practices can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

Within this broader context, WP7 analyses COVID-19's impact and response from the perspective of information communication, focussing specifically on how crisis communication was planned, how was it implemented and adapted, and how vulnerabilities were addressed over time. The specific research questions for WP7 that this synthesis seeks to address, are:

- **WP7 RQ1:** How and under which conditions were COVID-19 communication responses planned, implemented and adapted across diverse contexts and groups?
- **WP7 RQ2:** How have vulnerabilities been addressed and/or exacerbated by COVID-19 crisis communication responses?
- **WP7 RQ3:** Which barriers, unintended consequences, trade-offs, lessons learnt and promising practices can be identified in COVID-19 crisis communication responses across diverse local contexts?

The COVID-19 pandemic prompted a range of responses across different countries, reflecting their unique contexts, governance structures, and societal dynamics. The responses reveal successful strategies, lessons learnt, and challenges and adaptations that emerged over time. Here, we compare and synthesize the COVID-19 crisis communication responses in Austria, Belgium, England, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and Wales, focusing on how these responses were planned, implemented, and adapted across diverse local contexts and groups. In Chapter 3, we analyse the preparedness and planning of crisis communication before the pandemic started, and how the existing plans were adapted and implemented during the different stages of the pandemic. In Chapter 4, we analyse the different vulnerable groups that were acknowledged and the ways they were approached. We trace how this happened over time and the different strategies and approaches adopted by the ten countries. We pay special attention to the discrepancies between acknowledging certain vulnerabilities and actually implementing measures for inclusive communication, that actively contribute to reaching vulnerable groups. Chapter 5 is devoted to synthesizing the barriers and good practices. By doing this, it highlights the lessons learnt that could be used to manage future crises.

The deliverable is drawing on the updated country reports, country frames and the analysis of the key findings presented in D7.7 “Analysis: Communication and information - update M34”, and includes both analysis of secondary sources, and analysis of original empirical data from the expert interviews conducted for each of the ten countries. The detailed information for each country on which this synthesis draws, are presented in the country reports and country frames in D7.7.

2 Conditions, implementation and adaptation of COVID-19 communication responses

This section addresses the following research question: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 communication responses planned, implemented and adapted across diverse contexts and groups? We highlight the differences between the crisis communication plans available before the COVID-19 pandemic and the way crisis communication was implemented and adapted in the course of the pandemic in the different countries. We assess the changing strategies and we pay specific attention to how countries dealt with mal- and disinformation.

2.1 Crisis communication responses

Crisis communication in all countries was initially based on pre-existing national **crisis communication plans**, which most countries had integrated into their adaptation of the WHO pandemic influenza plan. However, most of the National Influenza Plans were quite old, having been implemented between 2006 and 2009, with the exception of Sweden and Germany. Sweden updated its plan in 2019 and Germany in 2017. Both England and Wales had adopted the UK-wide Pandemic Influenza Communications Strategy in 2012. In addition, before the COVID-19 outbreak, the Sweden's Public Health Agency had issued a separate guidance document on pandemic communication. In addition to outdated pandemic plans, the communication sections of the national influenza plans were not detailed enough and did not include comprehensive planning for engaging different vulnerable groups. For example, the German plan emphasises transparency and evidence-based messaging, and provides for different means of communication to overcome the digital divide. However, other vulnerabilities were not mentioned at all. Similarly, Portugal had a specific crisis communication plan, but it contained only guiding principles - such as addressing the crisis directly and transparently, avoiding merely informative and reactive communication, disseminating information in a timely manner and coordinating the approach of a cluster of entities in order to reduce anxiety, uncertainty, misperceptions and fear. However, it did not provide a concrete step-by-step plan for managing crisis communication effectively. On the other hand, countries such as Belgium and Italy had pre-existing crisis communication plans, but these were designed for crises such as natural disasters. In the case of Greece, the existing plans were designed for other specific health epidemics (Ebola, West Nile virus or malaria). As a result, many countries - such as Austria, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and Wales - had to quickly issue specific communication guidelines for the COVID-19 pandemic.

Responsibility for crisis communication also varied widely between countries and underwent fundamental changes. In most countries, the Prime Minister, and Ministries of Health, the Interior, or National Security were in charge of crisis communication. Some countries also used National crisis centres. However, due to the complexity of the crisis, experts such as Christian Dorsten from the Charité in Berlin for Germany, Anders Tegnell from the National Board of Health in Sweden or Sotiris Tsiordas, head of the committee of experts on infectious diseases in Greece, became the government advisors and the main public communicators informing the public. This was also the case in England and Wales, where the Chief Medical Officers for England, Wales and the UK as a whole were also responsible for crisis communication, but the Queen also had a crucial role. In Belgium, a new coronavirus commissioner was appointed, Pedro Facon, and in Italy, the role of extraordinary

commissioner for COVID-19 was taken over by a military officer, General of the Army Corps Francesco Paolo Figuolo.

Different governmental strategies played different roles, depending on the **centralised or federal government structure**. In order to act and communicate more coherently, Belgium declared a state of emergency to temporarily overcome the federalised government structure. In contrast to Belgium, Germany only enacted the "Gesetz zum Schutz der Gesundheit der Bevölkerung in epidemiologischen Situationen von überregionaler Bedeutung" (Law on the protection of public health in epidemiological situations of national importance), which temporarily gave the Ministry of Health more powers, but not in terms of communication. As a result, there was confusion among German citizens due to different regulations in the 16 federal states and insufficient communication. Later, an evaluation by the German government found that different roles and responsibilities needed to be clearly allocated and presented to the public in an understandable way. And although Wales had been given full sovereignty to manage the COVID-19 pandemic independently of the other UK nations, citizens following news from the UK were led to believe that the rules introduced by UK Prime Minister Boris Johnson also applied to them.

Many countries stated that too many actors were involved in crisis communication, which contributed to the sending of conflicting messages. However, this does not mean that cooperation between institutions and different types of professionals should be avoided. In Portugal, for example, coordination between health institutions and journalists was difficult at the beginning of the pandemic. This made it difficult for journalists to obtain reliable and official information. However, partnerships with journalists were later established and proved to be very fruitful, not least because the government did not have enough communication staff to fully take over the communication of key information. The role of journalists was also discussed in Greece, where the government was heavily criticised for not allowing journalists to ask questions directly. At the same time, in Wales and England, journalists brought a different dimension to crisis communication by interacting directly with citizens and responding to their information needs, but also by telling personal stories rather than focusing on dry figures.

On the other hand, the Belgian media was criticised for lacking scientific journalists, whilst in Germany, England and Spain media was said to report on COVID-19 too negatively instigating unnecessary fear and panic. In the same vein, Portugal had established a task force of behavioural scientists to advise the government on how citizens would comply with government recommendations, and Spain sought expert advice on epidemiology, virology and public health, which subsequently also informed government decision-making and crisis management strategies. With regard to hard-to-reach vulnerable groups, countries such as Austria, Greece, Belgium, Sweden, Portugal and Wales worked with civil society organisations and community representatives, also extending the centralised approach. In conclusion, both federal and non-federal states (Greece, Belgium, Portugal, Spain, Italy, Germany) followed a **centralised government approach** initially, and only later worked more closely with regional authorities, international organisations and sought advice from scientific experts to inform crisis management strategies.

Inclusive communication and acknowledging the different needs of different vulnerable groups is further discussed in more details in the next chapter.

2.2 Implementation of crisis communication

This broadening of communication responses goes hand in hand with a change in the communication strategies, such as communication principles, **means of communication** and content of communication. While all countries held weekly press conferences, provided information on government websites and in the media, and ran national information campaigns, Austria, Belgium and Wales also set up or reactivated health helplines to reach citizens. To inform those groups that couldn't be easily reached digitally, England resorted to sending letters and text messages. During the pandemic, several countries, including Austria, Italy, Germany and Portugal, also launched mobile phone applications to inform citizens whether they had been in contact with an infected person and what government restrictions were in place. Although this application failed in Portugal, it was well received in Germany and Austria.

The **content of the information** reported also changed over the course of the pandemic. While in the beginning countries focused on reporting health-related aspects (such as number of deaths, incidence rate, hospital beds occupied, risks and protective measures), over time reporting became more nuanced and addressed other vulnerable groups, like refugees, asylum seekers, the elderly, children, women at risk of domestic violence as well. Of course, the content also depended heavily on changing circumstances - such as virus mutations or the introduction of vaccines. While the initial interest was in flattening the curve and preventing infection, the focus then shifted to getting everyone vaccinated and returning to a 'normal' life. In this respect, Germany also shifted from seeing the virus as a threat only to certain at-risk groups to the population as a whole, and changed its communication tools and content accordingly. This change in the definition of who was at risk and who was affected by the pandemic was also seen in other countries. In Wales, for example, the focus has been on communicating that all citizens have a responsibility to contain the virus. And Belgium launched the "Antwerpen Helps" campaign, which emphasised the general well-being of the population and solidarity among them.

Over the course of the pandemic, another major shift occurred in regard to the **principles** behind the information communication which also influenced what content was disseminated. For instance, a Welsh expert concluded that the use of hard scientific data, such as reporting only infection or mortality rates, did not speak to the population in the same way. They suggested that it would be more beneficial to incorporate qualitative data, like personal stories. The same expert also stressed the necessity of disclosing any uncertainties. Spain and Germany stressed the importance of evidence-based and factual information to prevent unrest, while Austria and Greece concurred that complex issues should not be extensively covered in primary communication and could instead be reserved for specialized channels. This approach would avoid confusion while still providing detailed information for those interested. Other guiding principles included the provision of accurate, clear, timely, reliable, and respectful information (Italy, Sweden, Wales, Spain) using easy-to-understand visual aids and ensuring consistency throughout communication and content (England, Spain).

Also, the fighting of **mal- and disinformation** evolved over time and became more and more important. Government established task forces aiming at confining the spread of fake news. For example, in England, the Department for Digital, Culture, Media, and Sport played a role in fighting misinformation and disinformation within the context of COVID-19, and in Sweden, the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency was responsible for continuously monitoring and, where necessary, addressing misinformation, disinformation and rumour spreading about COVID-19 vaccination. In addition to this, government also established collaborations with media outlets or certain journalists – like in Portugal and Spain. Both Belgium and England collaborated with strategic communication experts. Additionally,

England implemented social media campaigns, as did Germany through the creation of a transparency website ("Frag den Staat"), and Spain via the launch of a fact-checking initiative and public awareness campaigns. Sweden disseminated information on misconceptions surrounding the COVID-19 virus and translated it into multiple languages, with a focus on vaccine-hesitant groups. Meanwhile, experts revealed that Sweden did not allocate enough resources to persuade or reach out to groups who adamantly reject vaccination, enabling them to focus more on those who are persuadable. Additionally, Portugal translated a UNESCO document aimed at countering disinformation. Sweden and Spain also monitored the dissemination of false information on social media and sought to counteract it with factual evidence, adhering to the aforementioned principles of objective, accurate, clear, and respectful communication.

Therefore, advising governmental communication by scientists also falls under the category of fighting mal- and disinformation. Further, the collaboration with experts could also be used to emphasise that the measures undertaken and vaccination is based on scientific research, a strategy applied by Belgium, Portugal and Spain. However, Spain explicitly tried not to label fake news as such but rather focused on offering truthful information and appealed to citizens to resort to reliable sources.

An important principle for combating fake news, which was applied in all countries, was to base published information on scientific knowledge. Thus, the role of scientists in advising the government's communication also included combating mal- and disinformation. Furthermore, collaborating with experts could emphasise that the measures taken and the vaccination campaigns are based on scientific research. This strategy was adopted by Belgium, Portugal, and Spain. However, Spain explicitly avoided categorising false information as "fake news" and chose instead to emphasise providing accurate information and the authorities appealed to citizens to rely on credible sources.

Finally, several countries chose to **evaluate their communication responses** in terms of their effectiveness in changing behaviour. This allowed governments to assess whether a practice was good or bad, and to change and adapt it if it was not effective. Greece focused on the effectiveness of different media channels to better tailor communication strategies, and evaluated vaccination successes to change or strengthen communication strategies in this area as well. In Belgium, the federal government worked with university experts to better understand the population's feelings, beliefs and trust in vaccination. While many countries evaluated the effectiveness of COVID-19 interventions and vaccination coverage, they did not always monitor the public's trust in government, the media and the content of government policies, nor did they take preventive action or change their communication strategy based on these surveys.

3 Vulnerabilities and access to communication and information

This section addresses the following research question, “How have vulnerabilities and access to communication and information been addressed and/or exacerbated by COVID-19 crisis communication responses?” It provides a synthesis of the main strategies adopted by governments to identify and recognise vulnerable groups in terms of access to information during the crisis, as set out in existing contingency plans, and how these strategies evolved in different countries over the course of the pandemic. The section discusses communication constraints and their unintended consequences. It also summarises the different ways in which vulnerable groups were represented in the media.

3.1 Identifying vulnerable groups

The definition of vulnerable groups changed over the course of the pandemic, as new vulnerable groups came to the fore as shortcomings in information dissemination and crisis communication management became more apparent. While at the beginning of the COVID-19 outbreak, vulnerability was defined primarily in terms of physical health, the focus broadened to include factors such as mental health, age, financial stability and occupational status, digital access, language skills (deaf, blind, simple language) and non-native speakers, as well as people with a migrant background as a whole. However, there are some differences between countries in terms of which categories were identified as vulnerable in the context of communication and information. While Austria also focused on seasonal workers, Italy launched a special campaign for women affected by domestic violence, Portugal and Greece included Roma people, and Wales included people experiencing homelessness. England and Sweden are an exception to this, as England had a broader understanding of vulnerability from the outset, including non-native speakers, the blind and deaf, people with disabilities, foreign nationals, asylum seekers and refugees. Similarly, Sweden adopted different communication strategies for groups with low socio-economic status, migrants and non-Swedish speakers, and only later adapted communication for people with disabilities, the chronically ill, obese or pregnant. Sweden was also able to rely on pre-existing knowledge of the PHA to tailor communication content and strategies to vulnerable groups, while other countries had pre-existing crisis communication management plans but lacked the identification of specific 'at risk' groups (Germany). Furthermore, the crisis management plans of Germany and Belgium were simply not designed for a crisis of such a long duration (Belgium, Germany). In addition, most crisis communication management plans or the official government communication strategy did not provide for separate communication with specific groups of the population and instead advocated a one-size-fits-all communication approach (e.g., Austria, Belgium).

3.2 Targeted communication measures

As the initial definition of vulnerability was quite narrow in most countries, the groups targeted by specific communication were also very few. All countries targeted the general public, but Austria and Italy also directly included older people, and Germany emphasised the need to bridge the digital divide by using different means of communication. England, Germany and Wales also focused on different ethnic groups, disseminating information in several languages, including sign language and special media for the blind. Germany, in particular, adopted an umbrella campaign with several sub-campaigns. The fact that certain segments of the population, especially those who do not speak the official languages, could not be reached by a single communication approach led all countries to launch

multilingual campaigns as the pandemic progressed. By disseminating information in several languages, countries sought to reach minority groups such as Roma (Portugal, Greece), sub-Saharan communities (Belgium), migrants, refugees and asylum seekers. A particularly effective strategy in this context was to work with civil society organisations (CSOs) and local representatives of vulnerable communities (Wales, England, Germany, Spain). Of course, because COVID-19 is a threat to people's health, medically vulnerable people and medical staff were also the focus of communication campaigns in all the countries analysed. In addition, countries other than Germany began to focus more on issues such as digital exclusion or the digital divide as the pandemic progressed, targeting different age groups such as older people, children and young people through different media and campaigns.

Despite all these efforts, certain segments of the population have not been adequately reached. For example, those with low levels of education or low socio-economic status. To reach those on low incomes, Spain made electronic devices available to them. Countries such as Wales, England, Sweden, Germany, Austria, Belgium and Italy also focused on people with low literacy skills or learning disabilities. For example, many countries tried to provide information in simple language on government websites. Another group that Sweden and Greece focused on was tailoring information to tourists or travellers, so communication was changed to reach these groups. Finally, over the course of the pandemic, all countries provided information in several languages, including sign language, and some even provided information in simple language.

In addition, information campaigns targeted at specific vulnerable groups served a dual purpose. In Wales, the aim was to disseminate information, but also to make these vulnerable groups more visible to society at large. Similarly, Germany used these campaigns to promote its lifestyle and cultural diversity. However, beyond simply making these groups more visible, countries such as Germany, Wales and Belgium emphasised the need to express solidarity with these groups through the campaigns. In Germany, for example, this solidarity focused on health care workers and culminated in many citizens expressing their gratitude by applauding these workers from their balconies or homes. In addition, this change in the representation of vulnerable groups was accompanied by a change in the definition of the groups affected by the virus. As noted above, COVID-19 was no longer seen as a risk only to certain more vulnerable groups, but to the population as a whole. This also marks a shift from an individual to a societal responsibility towards COVID-19.

4 Barriers, adaptation processes and lessons learnt

This section addresses the following research question, “What barriers, unintended consequences, trade-offs, lessons learnt, and promising practices can be identified in COVID-19 crisis communication responses in different local contexts?” It aims to assess all aspects of crisis communication, particularly in relation to the inclusion of vulnerable groups. While certain barriers and adaptation processes have already been discussed in previous sections, this section brings together good and bad practices and lessons learnt. Finally, it identifies the most common difficulties for which solutions have not yet been found.

4.1 Barriers and adaptation processes

One of the major barriers that became apparent immediately after the outbreak in February/March 2020 was the partial absence or inadequacy of crisis communication plans. As a direct consequence, this prevented countries from acting in line and communicating strategically in the immediate aftermath of the outbreak, and the implementation of a new communication plan took valuable time. As well as preventing countries from acting in time, this had wider consequences. These consequences become even more apparent when Sweden is compared with the cases of Belgium, Germany and Wales. Sweden was able to rely not only on pre-existing policies, but also on a high degree of legal autonomy for the Public Health Agency itself. This clear and strong division of responsibilities also enabled Sweden to reduce confusion. In order to manage the pandemic more effectively, Spain, Italy and Belgium declared a state of emergency, and Wales was given the power to manage the COVID-19 pandemic independently of the other UK nations. However, as the cases of Germany and Wales show, this division of responsibility did not always work well, leading to confusion among citizens about which sources to trust. On several occasions, government institutions even gave contradictory messages, further undermining citizens' trust in government. This was the case when Austria announced the introduction of compulsory vaccination, only to reverse it, or when the Welsh government promised to be able to receive around 9000 test results a day, and then failed to do so. It's not only important for governments to be realistic, but also to be honest with their citizens and not, as in the case of Spain, claim that the masks are not effective in preventing infection with the COVID-19 virus, when in fact there were simply not enough masks.

In addition, by outsourcing pandemic management to the National Public Health Agency in Sweden, **health experts and scientists** have been intrinsically involved in pandemic communication, thereby increasing the credibility of the information and the public's trust in government decisions and communication. Involving experts in decision-making about communication processes not only ensures that information about the pandemic is valid, but also prevents politicians from making promises they cannot keep and using the crisis for political gain, as politicians in Austria, Wales and Spain have done. As a consequence, it also leads to an erosion of citizens' trust in government and its ability to deliver. Working with experts is also essential when it comes to misinformation, as it is better to **combat misinformation** before it arises rather than after it has spread. By scientifically underpinning government decisions and recommendations, experts also ensure - as mentioned above - that politicians do not make false promises, thereby strengthening citizens' trust and potentially preventing the personal need to adhere to an alternative worldview, i.e., misinformation. Another way to increase citizens' trust in government decisions was to increase the **bidirectionality of communication** or to integrate citizens' criticism, thus generating a general discussion. Spain set up channels not only to

disseminate information, but also to receive feedback, questions, advice and doubts about the measures. Spain also later emphasised the need to publish the reports of the Scientific and Technical Committee so that the public could better understand the decision-making process.

However, countering misinformation cannot be done by government agencies alone, but requires cooperation with media associations, journalists, regional authorities and civil society organisations. Media and other organisations have additional resources that they can use to disseminate information and counter misinformation, they can draw on existing networks, and they can reach out to different groups in society and reach out to those who have been neglected by the government. Working with community representatives also has the added advantage of being more trusted by their peers. Another positive aspect is that working directly with communities can encourage community involvement and active participation in decision-making processes, which in turn promotes a sense of ownership and compliance with public health measures.

However, it is important to ensure that crisis communication is coordinated at government, NGO and media levels. If communication strategies are not aligned and contradictory messages are sent out, this will fuel the spread of mistrust and misinformation. One way to achieve this is to provide **communication guidelines**, as the case of Wales shows. The internal document served as a basis for all institutions involved in crisis communication (governmental, non-governmental, media) to keep the messages consistent. The guide should also include information on **communication principles** that have proved effective. Information must be respectful, evidence-based but not highly scientific, accurate, clear, timely and stress the need for individual and collective responsibility. Just as governments in Portugal were criticised for not communicating in simple language, journalists in Wales and England tried to fill this gap by providing stories and not just quantitative data on COVID-19, making its effects and risks more accessible to many citizens.

Finally, Sweden's pre-existing contingency plan included information on potentially vulnerable groups, and the Public Health Agency not only had knowledge of how to reach vulnerable groups, but could also draw on **pre-existing networks** that needed to be reactivated rather than created from scratch. As a result, Sweden gained valuable time and had to invest fewer resources in the initial establishment of these networks. In addition, working together at regional or non-governmental level can be more effective in reaching vulnerable groups, especially if there is already a mistrust of government among them. However, this collaboration with regional government or civil society organisations can only be helpful in reaching vulnerable or hard-to-reach groups if a holistic understanding of vulnerability has been adopted beforehand. In England, Germany and Wales, the use of different communication tools and languages in their communication strategies allowed them to save time and reach these groups directly and effectively. A **holistic definition of vulnerability** must therefore be built into crisis communication plans in advance. This will not only ensure that all governments are known to all citizens, but also that information is disseminated quickly and in such a way that all segments of society understand what countries are doing. This also allows for a more unified and timely response to the crisis.

However, there are still certain **difficulties and challenges** that either do not yet have an appropriate solution or cannot be addressed in advance because the circumstances of the crisis are not yet known. Of course, no two crises are alike. But the difficulty of dealing with uncertainty must be recognised, as experts in Portugal, Sweden, Wales, Germany and Spain have done. At a more general level, the management of any crisis always faces the challenge of striking a balance between reassuring citizens and accurately illustrating the scale of the threat. In this context, it is important to bear in mind that

perceptions of risk vary and that multiple communication campaigns and strategies are essential. Also new during the COVID-19 pandemic was the phenomenon of "pandemic fatigue", due to the unprecedented longevity of the crisis. Although Sweden, Portugal and Spain recognised the need to keep citizens motivated over a longer period of time, no solution is offered. Moreover, there is a risk that the crisis will be neglected when several other crises occur. This also points to the need to communicate the danger of a crisis accurately and to cover it widely.

4.2 Lessons learnt

Crisis management and communication plans must be existent prior to the outbreak of a crisis and take different forms of crisis into consideration. Furthermore, crisis management must entail a detailed plan on how to communicate a crisis, hence it is imperative to collaborate with experts such as communication experts or behavioural psychologists. Especially the communication plan must be thorough and a holistic understanding of vulnerabilities must be applied. Furthermore, the plans must be detailed but allow a flexible application and plan for longer time periods of a crisis as especially the cases of Belgium and Germany show. A good crisis communication management must also be evaluated timely and periodically regarding good and bad practices, as well as lessons learnt. These lessons must then be integrated in the crisis management plan.

The **distribution of responsibilities** for crisis communication management needs to be clear, and decision-making and communication need to be centralised. The lack of coordinated efforts and clear division of roles between national and regional authorities created confusion and slowed down clear communication. Ambiguous messages from different governmental institutions increased citizens' confusion, enabled the spread of misinformation about the COVID-19 pandemic, thereby increasing the uncertainty of COVID-19 information and, in the long term, reducing citizens' trust in the media, politics and governmental capabilities. Cooperation with federal or non-governmental institutions and media associations is also necessary, for example to reach vulnerable groups, but responsibilities and the content of the information must be clearly defined beforehand. The involvement of civil society organisations, federal institutions or media associations needs to be immediate in order to avoid confusion about crisis information and management from the outset. In order to benefit from the links established during the crisis, it is essential to maintain these collaborations beyond the actual crisis. This will facilitate their reactivation in the event of another crisis.

Experts need to be involved at all levels of policy-making and crisis communication management. It is also essential to know what measures are feasible and to admit uncertainty or ignorance. Politicians should not use the crisis to promote their own political ideas, as this further undermines citizens' overall trust in politics. In addition, guidelines and reports issued by scientific committees or political bodies should be published so that the public can understand the decision-making process and thereby increase their trust in politics. Of course, the involvement of scientists in decision-making in general allows issues to be addressed in greater depth. Moreover, as the experience of a crisis can be very anxiety-provoking, leading to a sense of overwhelm and information overload among citizens, communication and psychology experts can assess how to change communication or nudge citizens to achieve the expected outcome.

Regular evaluation of crisis management and crisis communication is necessary. As stated in 2a. above, crisis communication must be centralised, but this does not mean that crisis management must be a top-down, one-way process. Rather, crisis management must be flexible and therefore integrate feedback loops and evaluate them regularly. Crisis communication management should therefore

involve many actors at the same time, ranging from state and federal institutions to the media, civil society organisations, professional associations and crisis units. These evaluations of good and bad practices and lessons learnt should be incorporated not only into current crisis management but also into future preparedness plans.

Communication must follow certain **principles** in order to provide information to all citizens in an understandable and consistent way. Communication must be tailored to reach specific audiences, especially those who are hard to reach. A one-size-fits-all approach to communication should therefore be avoided, although the launch of overarching umbrella campaigns and several sub-campaigns can be useful, as the German case shows. Diversifying communication means using multiple means of communication to overcome the digital divide, such as traditional and digital media. In addition, information must be disseminated in different languages for non-native speakers, be easy to understand, for example by including strong visual keys, and also take into account people with cognitive, visual or hearing impairments. Overall, communication needs to apply a holistic understanding of vulnerability in order to address everyone equally, which will be discussed in more detail in the section on vulnerability.

Making information understandable to all goes hand in hand with tackling **misinformation**. First and foremost, information must be based on scientific evidence, while acknowledging scientific ignorance and uncertainty on certain issues. Crisis communication management also has to walk the tightrope between communicating immediately, yet accurately and validly, and ensuring that the uncertainty of the information is appropriately conveyed to the public. Another aspect is the transparent communication of decisions and the fact that they are based on science. Therefore, experts need to be involved in communication management. Experts should be familiar with the topic of the crisis (e.g. for COVID-19, virology, epidemiology), but experts in communication and behavioural psychology should always be involved. In addition, information needs to be coherent and therefore coordinated by a key actor, and, as mentioned above, government communication guidelines need to be in place before a crisis occurs and updated regularly.

The final lesson relates to **vulnerable groups**, as they need to be addressed in specific ways, in addition to the mainstream information and communication provided. The main lesson is to adopt a broader definition of those groups that can be considered vulnerable, and then pay additional attention to possible new vulnerabilities triggered by the concrete crisis. What we have seen in the COVID-19 pandemic is that pre-existing vulnerabilities were exacerbated, but also that new types of vulnerabilities were triggered by the specificity of the crisis itself. Communication needs to be adapted accordingly and therefore provided in multiple languages, including sign language, Braille and simple language to reach citizens with lower levels of education, and disseminated through different media to reach citizens of all ages, e.g. children and young people through social media and older people through more traditional media.

5 Conclusion

Vulnerability is a flexible category, activated in different ways and to different degrees depending on the context. Crisis communication needs to be adapted to the specific needs of groups at risk of exclusion from mainstream communication. Most countries did not have a comprehensive understanding of potential vulnerabilities in their crisis plans. This led to delayed inclusion, and only of certain groups. Initially, communication was implemented through a one-size-fits-all approach aimed at the majority. At a later stage, most countries adopted inclusive channels and means of information. However, many groups remained excluded for a long time, which also created mistrust and allowed false information to spread.

Although **communication responses** were partly based on **pre-existing crisis communication plans**, these were often not thorough enough or applicable to a crisis of such scale and duration. Countries' response plans depended heavily on the existing government structure, which in some cases was changed to deal with the crisis in a more centralised way. However, most countries adopted a **centralised, top-down approach** from the outset of the pandemic and a one-size-fits-all communication approach based on traditional communication channels and social media. As this often proved insufficient, countries were forced to adapt and broaden their communication response as the pandemic progressed.

For example, while still acting centrally, countries adapted their strategies to work with sub-national or non-governmental institutions (CSOs). Expert committees were also set up or consulted to better influence public behaviour or combat misinformation and disinformation. In addition, the content of communication has been modified according to current pandemic-related events and the style of communication has been adapted to minimise fear and information overload.

Research must be linked to policy-making. Social sciences in all countries have sufficient empirical data on existing vulnerabilities. The crisis has led to even more research on these very issues. The challenge is to ensure that this research reaches policy-makers and is taken into account, so that vulnerable groups are included in contingency plans and measures from the outset of a future crisis.

Crisis management is not a unilateral, top-down approach. It is multi-dimensional, involves many actors and should immediately incorporate feedback from different groups (CSOs, professional associations, etc.) and adapt in a timely manner. **Continuous evaluation** of activities is necessary.

The vulnerabilities that came to the fore during the COVID-19 pandemic are many, but not new. It is therefore essential to integrate a **holistic definition of vulnerability** into national contingency plans in order to reach all segments of the population and to adapt communication strategies and information accordingly. Some governments have already done this, reaffirming that COVID-19 communication must be inclusive (England) or publishing a guideline on how municipalities can address vulnerable groups (Germany). Future plans must therefore model different crisis scenarios with a high degree of **flexibility**.

